

**From The Collapse of Arabism to Sectarian Citizenship: How Religion and Tribalism
Determine National Belonging in Lebanon and Saudi Arabia**

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World War I—“The Great War” and the years that ensued were a time of great upheaval in the Middle East, launching, amplifying, and compounding pre-existing sectarian divides of Lebanon and Saudi Arabia among citizens and tribes of the two nations. Although a weak form of Arabism had already begun to emerge in the decades preceding the war, the conflict's outcome and commitments made for Arab self-determination without external compulsion, the War's victors (Britain and France) had treated the region as a prize of conquest, which helped the spread of Arabism. However, in the struggle to defeat the Ottomans and the helplessness of Arab fighting forces, hollow promises were made by Britain and France to the indigenous Arab populations. The McMahon-Hussein correspondence and the infamous Sykes-Picot Agreement of 1916 had catalyzed the colonial powers to draw arbitrary borders and divide Arab lands into British and French territories of control, leaving a fractured Arab World in its wake (*The Failure of the Arab Spring*, 2016). The involvement of the Hashamite family of Hijaz under Sharif Hussain (followers of Sunni Islam) with France and Britain had significant consequences, particularly for the Shia community in the nation of Saudi Arabia. Wahhabism, central to the Saudi state's national identity, was deeply antagonistic to Shiism, which had set the stage for conflict as a result of the brewing religious sectarian influences. In Lebanon, a slippery slope was taking shape after French interference had formalized sectarianism through French Mandate authorities that reinforced the notion of religious affiliation as a key political marker that would dominate Lebanese politics and national belonging (*Syria and Lebanon Under the French Mandate*, 2018). This paper explains that in the nations of Lebanon and Saudi Arabia, foreign influence and internal cleavages, the institutionalization of sectarianism in citizenship, and historical continuity and transformation collectively define and continually reshape national belonging through religious affiliation. Exploring how outside and inside forces redefine the ‘malleability’ of Arab national identity and belonging vis-à-vis sectarian influences.

In continuation, the occurrences of *foreign* influence in Lebanon evidence the lasting marks of religious and tribal sects on national belonging. External forces and *foreign* influence remained a consequential driving force, as they marked fundamental consequences in worsening overall nationhood, and patriotism declined. The Sykes-Picot Agreement of 1916, which followed the collapse of the Ottoman Empire, marks the beginning of a postcolonial centralization due to the San Remo Conference, a formal distribution of territories organized by the French mandate. The reason the French mandate was of importance was rooted in creating a pro-French, Christian-dominated state, favoring Maronite Christians both politically and economically (*Redrawing the Middle East*, 2018). In consequence, this tipped the scales in favor of Lebanese Christians, due to the prior weakness of the national Arab identity as a political force. This also had lasting effects on the Sunnis, Shi'a, and Druze sects, as they were at a disadvantage in outweighing the power of the Maronites, supported by the French. Eventually, these tensions soon escalated into violent clashes. One instance is the Druze's direct and often violent clashes

with the Maronites. The massacres and subsequent French intervention not only set a precedent for foreign involvement in sectarian affairs but had laid the groundwork for the French mandate's later sectarian model of governance in Lebanon. With the weak sense of patriotism having largely dissipated, and both power and position determining national belonging in Lebanon, over time, these imbalances worsened, following the 1948 Arab-Israeli War. During that time, the consequences of the presence of the armed influence of the Palestine Liberation Organization (PLO) provoked substantial tensions among segments of the Lebanese population. The effects of the PLO's involvement, marked by its armed operations from Lebanese territory against Israel, effectively aligned Lebanon with Muslim political factions, in opposition to Christian groups. As a result, this dynamic further burdened existing sectarian divisions and played a crucial role in the outbreak of the Lebanese Civil War. However, despite decades of conflict and political reconstruction, the Lebanese people had yet to reach a unified understanding of nationhood that encompasses all sects and communities together. When state institutions weakened under the strain of such long-standing divisions, although predating the war, became increasingly more severe, forcing Lebanon to confront an intense civil conflict. This conflict, infamously known as 'The Lebanese Civil War' of 1975-1990, began as the gruesome accumulation of the aforementioned tensions, with sectarianism becoming the main driving force of the war. During this period, an individual's sect increasingly determined where they stood, including national identity both politically and socially. When complications escalated in 1975, Saudi Arabia and Syria's involvement was intended to reaffirm Lebanon's sovereignty and call for mutual coexistence among its religious communities in Lebanon via the 'Taif agreement' (1989), which had been negotiated under complex international and regional pressures. Consequently, fulfilling the agreement meant diminishing the authority the Maronites had previously presided over while strengthening foreign powers in Lebanon, in the name of "peacekeeping". This shift soon paved the way for Hezbollah's role in Lebanese politics, particularly after the Taif agreement, which has been a major factor in the country's ongoing instability. The reasons for this are particularly due to the 'Taif agreement', which had neglected the grounds that 'propelled' the Civil War to erupt initially. The conditions of the Taif agreement meant that Hezbollah was permitted to maintain its military wing due to its role in resisting the Israeli occupation. Over time, this led to the gradual increase of Hezbollah's authority, which ultimately caused Hezbollah to become a powerful political and military force. Ultimately, Hezbollah's refusal to disarm also became a larger issue due to its close ties to external factors, leading to overall political stagnation and vulnerability to deepened divisions (*Redrawing the Middle East*, 2018). Hence, the effects of such interferences in Lebanon had lasting effects, reinforcing the power of the mercantile elite and the impacts of external influences on the politically and culturally unstable Lebanon. At its core, this issue mainly stems from the failure of *internally* addressing the recurring cycles of sectarianism. This concept aids in framing the analysis of geopolitical influence in the Middle Eastern region, beneficial for understanding how sectarianism persists as a recognized facet of

Lebanese society post-colonialism. The French Mandate's influence on Lebanon emerges as a fundamental catalyst setting the tone for the institutionalisation of sectarianism in the modern confessional structure of Lebanon (*Redrawing the Middle East*, 2018). While acknowledging other contributing factors remains important, this legacy laid the groundwork for the eventual fragmentation, fueled by the rise of Hezbollah, the aforementioned Taif Agreement, and many others. Likewise, the Taif Agreement, which, backed by Syria and Iran, advanced a radicalized Shia agenda that challenged the established sectarian order (Alagha, 2014). As Hezbollah's radicalized Shia agenda gained traction, Hezbollah gradually saw a national spike in the numbers of its members and supporters, due to welfare programs predominantly financed through Iran and sentiments among Shia citizens disillusioned with a state that prioritized sect over civic identity. In doing so, Hezbollah anchored itself in extended external alliances and religious affiliations. This transformation, in essence, has left a lasting impact on Lebanon, where belonging and power were controlled by elitist and external interferences, rather than a cohesive national identity with the necessary conventional balances.

Complementing this, Hezbollah's alignment with Iran reflects Lebanon's entanglement in broader Saudi-Iranian geopolitical rivalries. Accusations that Hezbollah serves Iranian interests over Lebanon's security reflect a broader pattern of Sunni-Shia tensions driven by the regional power struggle between Iran and Saudi Arabia. These sectarian divisions can be traced back to long-standing rivalries between Sunnis in Saudi Arabia and Shias in Iran (Alagha, 2014). As a consequence, this shaped Saudi Arabia's internal divisions, which continued to provoke significantly worsened sectarian divisions. Initially, when Saudi Arabia's government and its national security apparatus perceived any threats to them of a united front of citizens, sectarianism was seen as the ultimate fighting tool from their perspective. Rather than a consistent approach, Saudi rulers adjusted their sectarian tactics in response to shifting political landscapes. As Madawi al-Rasheed explains, although authority and isolation remain constant, "there is no regular and predictable strategy deployed by Saudi authoritarianism against Shias. Each historical moment requires a response towards this community, [particularly] straightforward repression" (Freer, 2019). Other testimonies mention the following: "As you see, we live on top of the oil, I see how it is being taken out of our soil daily. But you also see that our grass areas are poor, and we do not get a fair share of the oil income," expresses a Saudi Shia resident (Böttcher, 2002). Narratives like such underscore the economic marginalization of Shia communities in oil-rich regions, such as the Eastern Province, where, despite living atop vast natural wealth, the Shia community has been systematically excluded from its benefits. The Shia population in Saudi Arabia is largely concentrated in specific regions of the kingdom and faces both systemic and structural discrimination in favor of the Sunni majority. This entrenched marginalization not only reinforces sectarian divisions but also fosters hostility between the two communities (Böttcher, 2002). Given this context, it is rather predictable that Shias are often treated as social outcasts within their society, as evidenced by

their exclusion from security services, discriminatory rhetoric of the Sunni religious establishments, and biased portrayals within the nation's education system. Other sources emphasize the discrimination faced by Shia communities, from preventing them from joining influential sectors such as the petrochemical industry and restrictions on their access to higher education (Alagha, 2014). As a result, it is illustrated that Shias are treated as social pariahs in both social and economic conventions. The recurring societal alienation practiced in this case employs a heavily abused authoritarian political strategy developed by the Saudi *ulema* and religious scholars since the first Saudi state under Shaykh Muhammad Ibn Abd al-Wahhab. This has historically extended and institutionalized the previously addressed acts of exclusion towards the Shia population, where the nation manages to legitimize its exclusive grasp on power and authority. As a consequence of such, it influences public perceptions and plants a fractured sense of belonging through the dissemination of animosity and harmful rhetoric (Freer, 2019). As a consequence, the marginalization of the Shia community has been linked to harmful implications daily, such as systematic barriers to accessing career opportunities. Whether in its modern nation-state form or earlier political configurations, pastoralism can be understood as a form of civic devotion or a reflection of collective moral values. However, since the nation's collective values vary from claiming a stake in power and creating division, the case seems to exemplify an utterly weak sense of nationalism and patriotism, resulting in a negligible level of collective cohesion from the lens of society and government. The recurring weak sense of patriotism, conceptually and in its absence within societal unity, can be traced back to the 18th-century alliance between Muhammad Ibn Saud and Muhammad Ibn Abd al-Wahhab, which laid the foundation for the early favoring of the Sunni doctrine. Not only this, but events such as the formation of the first Saudi state in 1744 had their roots in the Wahhabi ideology and entrenched Shia exclusion as a feature of governance as a consequence. In short, the weak sense of congruence due to events such as the pivotal alliance between influential high-ranking officials laid the foundation for the favoring of the Sunni doctrine remarkably early on. Such prominent events, such as the formation of the first Saudi state in 1744, have rooted themselves in the Wahhabi ideology and systematic Shia exclusion to 'exterminate' the possibility of resistance or protests, which are inevitable when meaningful change fails to occur.

In a nutshell, this paper demonstrates that in Lebanon and Saudi Arabia, external influence and inner divisions, the institutionalization of sectarianism in citizenship, and historical continuity and change collectively continually reshape national belonging through religious affiliation. Demonstrating how external and internal factors redefine the national identity vis-à-vis sectarian influences. To recap, this was presently evidenced in how specific state practices reveal the intersection of sectarian identity with economic and national priorities. Instances such as the suppression of Shia communities are closely tied to broader regional dynamics involving identity politics and control over oil reserves. The Eastern Province, which is where

the Shia population predominantly resides in Saudi Arabia, paradoxically serves as both the economic heartland of the nation due to its vast oil reserves and marks the center of political marginalization. Despite the community's (Shia) substantial contributions to the nation's wealth, there remain residents who are systematically excluded from its economic benefits, underscoring how national identity in Saudi Arabia is shaped intricately by sectarian and economic inequalities. However, in Lebanon, identity was shaped by frameworks that linked religious affiliation to political representation, ensuring that citizens were Maronite, Sunni, Shia, or Druze, first, and Lebanese, second. While academic research suggests that religious diversity often contributes to progress socially and 'cohesion', the Lebanese confessional system is crippled with inefficiency in meeting the demands of its people. This type of confessional system is a kind of control that assigns governmental and decision-making positions based on affiliations to faith and religion, which confirms the representation of the officially recognized sects in Lebanon. This system encourages Lebanon's political authorities to alienate and estrange diverse sects from each other by employing sectarian resentments that date back to the Ottoman Empire. More so, this system entitles these political executives to stay in authority on the condition that they represent their followers' religious identities; this practice is best labeled as sectarianisation (Alagha, 2014). While it is paramount to acknowledge that the French colonial administration played a climactic role in Lebanese sectarianism, it is not the sole determinant of the examined outcome. Sectarian roots of external influences, the Ottoman era, and internal power struggles have also contributed to Lebanon's modern political landscape. As long as national belonging is filtered through the lens of sectarian loyalty, the possibility of a unified civic identity remains elusive—and perhaps intentionally so.

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